

Effect of Time on the Hydrolysis of Different Indian Basic Slags

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It has been observed that Burnpur, Bhadrabati Open-hearth Furnace, Bhadrabati Electric Furnace, Rourkela, Durgapur, Tata and Bhilai basic slags are hydrolysed by water liberating small amounts of lime and phosphoric acid in the solution. The rate of hydrolysis of all these slags decreases quickly with time but the hydrolysis continues for several days. Thus, when these Indian basic slags will be added to soil as fertilizers they can maintain a fairly constant supply of both lime and phosphoric acid, which are essential for the plant growth for a long interval of time. The experimental results show that the maximum amount of P_2O_5 passes into solution in the case of Tata basic slag, whereas the maximum amount of lime passes with Bhilai basic slag. The results further indicate that Indian basic slags except Bhadrabati Electric Furnace and Rourkela are as efficient as foreign basic slags e.g., German and Belgian basic slags from the lime solubilization point of view but they are inferior to the latter from the P_2O_5 solubilization view point.

THE importance of basic slags in crop production has been advocated by several workers¹⁻⁶.

Besides phosphate and lime basic slag also contains iron, manganese, potassium and magnesium. Consequently basic slag can also be used for the purpose of correcting soil deficiencies of these elements. It is likely that basic slag can also become one of the best shotgun prescriptions for nutrient crop deficiencies.

Recently Dhar and Pant⁷ and Pant and Pathak⁸ have studied the effect of time on the hydrolysis of some naturally occurring rock phosphates, basic slags and superphosphate but so far a systematic study of Indian basic slags has not been carried out. Therefore in the present paper an attempt has been made to study the effect of time on the hydrolysis of Burnpur, Bhadrabati Open-hearth Furnace, Bhadrabati Electric Furnace, Rourkela, Durgapur, Tata and Bhilai basic slags.

Experimental

All the samples of basic slags used in these experiments were analysed⁹ for P_2O_5 , lime and magnesia contents. 1 gm each of different basic slags, sieved through a 100 mesh sieve was taken in Jena glass

bottles and 100 ml of double distilled water were added to it. The bottles were kept in a thermostat maintained at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. Different sets were used for different intervals of time (e.g., 1, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 150, 200, 250 and 300 days). The contents of the bottles were stirred daily. After the definite intervals of time the bottles were taken out from the thermostat and shaken for one hour in a mechanical shaker and allowed to stand for some time. The contents of the bottles were then filtered. Aliquot portions of the filtrates were utilized for determining pH, electrical conductivity, lime¹⁰ and P_2O_5 .¹⁰

A magic eye conductivity bridge (Laboratory model) S.N. 182 and portable Cambridge pH meter were utilized for conductivity and pH determinations respectively. The following abbreviations have been used for different Indian and foreign basic slags.

Burnpur basic slag (Bur.B.S.), Bhadrabati Open-hearth Furnace basic slag (Bha.O.B.S.), Bhadrabati Electric Furnace basic slag (Bha.E.B.S.), Rourkela basic slag (R.B.S.), Durgapur basic slag (D.B.S.), Tata basic slag (T.B.S.), Bhilai basic slag (Bhi.B.S.), German basic slag (G.B.S.) and Belgian basic slag (B.B.S.).

TABLE I—ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT INDIAN BASIC SLAGS

%	Bur. B.S.	Bha. O.B.S.	Bha. E.B.S.	R.B.S.	D.B.S.	T.B.S.	Bhi. B.S.	G.B.S. ¹¹	B.B.S. ¹¹
CaO	41.719	39.390	34.100	33.330	36.053	32.732	43.492	42.346	41.685
P_2O_5	3.584	0.884	0.517	0.260	3.214	7.841	1.497	17.868	16.664
MgO	6.382	11.459	8.890	6.235	6.282	6.236	9.453	4.968	4.679
Available P_2O_5 2% citric acid	1.923	0.432	0.251	0.142	0.167	4.025	0.786	7.967	7.636

TABLE 2
After 24 hr

Sample	Gram per litre		pH	Specific conductivity in mhos $\times 10^{-4}$
	CaO	P ₂ O ₅		
Bur. B.S.	0.08764	0.00278	9.05	3.788
Bha. O.B.S.	0.06946	0.00085	9.15	2.556
Bha. E.B.S.	0.02277	0.00045	7.95	1.108
R.B.S.	0.02092	0.00021	7.65	0.979
D.B.S.	0.09094	0.00266	10.40	4.905
T.B.S.	0.04583	0.00688	8.30	1.511
Bhi. B.S.	0.10473	0.00136	10.75	5.034

TABLE 3
After 300 days

Sample	Gram per litre		pH	Specific conductivity in mhos $\times 10^{-4}$
	CaO	P ₂ O ₅		
Bur. B.S.	0.14823	0.00545	10.60	7.025
Bha. O.B.S.	0.14201	0.00181	10.70	5.850
Bha. E.B.S.	0.05401	0.00083	9.10	2.751
R.B.S.	0.05123	0.00045	9.05	2.675
D.B.S.	0.18487	0.00537	11.20	7.425
T.B.S.	0.10055	0.01165	9.70	4.312
Bhi. B.S.	0.18634	0.00262	11.35	7.574

Discussion

The experimental results recorded in Table 2 show that Bur.B.S., Bha.O.B.S., Bha.E.B.S., R.B.S., D.B.S., T.B.S. and Bhi.B.S. are hydrolysed by water liberating small amounts of lime and phosphoric acid in the solution. It has been observed that the hydrolysis of all the slags continues for several days but the rate of hydrolysis decreases quickly with time. With Bha.O.B.S. and T.B.S. the increase of lime and P₂O₅ continues upto 150 days and with Bur.B.S., Bha.E.B.S., R.B.S., D.B.S. and Bhi.B.S. upto 200 days and then there is a slight fall in the values. These results are also supported by the conductivity measurements.

The decrease in the solubility of all these basic slags after several days may be due to the fact that the aqueous solutions of all these slags contain Mg⁺⁺, Ca⁺⁺, PO₄⁻⁻, HPO₄⁻⁻ and OH⁻ ions and it is probable that in the course of time basic phosphates are likely to be formed which are less soluble than the original phosphates resulting in the partial removal of OH⁻ ions and thereby decreasing the conductivity and solubility. The decrease in the solubility may also

be due to the adsorption of released phosphate ions by the oxides of iron and aluminium, which are present in the basic slags. In all these experiments the maximum time allowed has been 300 days and if more time is allowed it is likely that these absorbed ions may again be released into the solutions due to the phenomenon of ageing.

It has been observed that the pH of the aqueous solutions of all these Indian slags is invariably on the alkaline side. The pH values of all these slags have been found to increase with the lapse of time indicating that more of lime than phosphoric acid passes into the solutions. These observations are in agreement with the solubility results.

It has been observed that among all these Indian basic slags the maximum amounts of P₂O₅ and lime pass into the solution with T.B.S. and Bhi.B.S. respectively. The results show that from the lime solubilization point of view these slags can be arranged in the order of Bhi.B.S. > D.B.S. > Bur.B.S. > Bha.O.B.S. > T.B.S. > Bha.E.B.S. > R.B.S. whereas from the P₂O₅ solubilization point of view the order is T.B.S. > Bur.B.S. > D.B.S. > Bhi.B.S. > Bha.O.B.S. > Bha.E.B.S. > R.B.S.

Pant¹² has observed that German and Belgian basic slags are hydrolysed by water. According to him, the amounts of P₂O₅ and lime passing into the solution are 0.01651 and 0.10236 g/litre with German basic slag and 0.01422 and 0.09166 g/litre with Belgian basic slag after 24 hr at 30°. On comparing these results with the results obtained with the Indian basic slags it is evident that all the Indian basic slags except Bha.E.B.S. and R.B.S. are as efficient as Belgian and German basic slags from the lime solubilization point of view but they are inferior to them from P₂O₅ solubilization view point.

The experimental observations recorded in the present paper clearly show that when these Indian basic slags will be applied to soil in finely ground form, they can maintain a fairly constant supply of both lime and phosphoric acid which are essential for the efficient growth of plants. As basic slags are rich in lime and magnesia contents, they can slowly and partly convert the very sparingly soluble phosphates of iron, titanium, and aluminium present in acidic soils into more soluble calcium and magnesium phosphates which are more easily assimilated by plants. Consequently in order to obtain a profitable phosphate fertilization, it will be of great importance to regulate and maintain the soil reaction near neutrality by proper liming with basic slags, to increase the available phosphate status of acidic soils all over the world.

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